

QUASI-DISTRIBUTED PRESSURE SENSORS EMBEDDED INTO SURFACE MATERIALS ON COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, upcoated and buffered optical fibres with Fibre Bragg Gratings (FBGs) have been used as quasi-distributed pressure sensors that can be embedded into surface materials for composite structures. The main goal has been to develop compact and robust sensors/sensor materials that measure pressures from 10 to 200 kPa.

The sensor used for this experiment was FBGs inscribed in 125 μ m optical fiber having either Polyimide (PI) or Acrylate (Ac) as original coating. The wavelength shift of an FBG can be related to strain, and its sensitivity is approximately 1.2 pm/ μ strain. To make the FBG sensitive to pressure, the optical fibers with FBGs were coated with a soft up-coating layer of silicone and a stiffer buffer material. The total outer diameter was 1 mm. Four buffered fibre cables were manufactured with combinations of the two original coating materials and two different buffer materials that were either Polyamide (PA) or Polyetheretherketone (PEEK).

The buffered optical fibres were embedded into a couple of different types of surface materials on top of pre-cured 4 mm carbon fibre /epoxy (CFRP) laminates. The surface material was either a syntactic foam material with a 0.1 mm glass fibre/epoxy cover layer or 10 epoxy film layers (36 gsm Hexel 6376 resin) with a 0.1 mm glass fibre/epoxy cover layer. The pressure response of the inbuilt optical fibres was tested in an Instron Machine in the load range of 10 to 200 kPa.

The best combination for pressure sensitivity was either to use an optical fibre with PI coating and PEEK buffer or an optical fibre with Ac coating and PA buffer combined with the syntactic foam surface cover material.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre Bragg Gratings (FBGs) are sensitive to external parameters, such as strain and temperature. Their high multiplexing capabilities allows the manufacturing of extremely dense sensing arrays in a single optical fibre, enabling highly localized measurements over a distributed area and making them attractive for structural health monitoring.

Extensive research and development have been performed using FBGs as pressure sensors in a variety of harsh environment applications such as thermoelectric power plant combustion chamber [1] (Rosolem et al) and filament wound pressure tanks [2] (Kang et al). Since FBG-based solutions are intrinsically poorly sensitive to external pressure, it is necessary to convert external pressure to

fibre elongation, more conveniently measured with FBGs and thus increasing the pressure sensitivity of these devices. Thus, the performance analysis of pressure sensors using different types of fibre Rodriguez et al [3] and packaging designs such as flexible diaphragm [4] (Liang et al), polymers [5] (Zhang et al) and bourdon tubes [6] (Huang et al) was addressed in several studies, achieving pressure sensitivities up to 280 nm/MPa Sebastian et al [7].

In the aeronautics scenario, Chehura et al [8], demonstrated FBG-based pressure sensors effectively applied to measure pressure on aircraft wings. When compared to traditional pressure sensors, FBG-based technique enables a much higher density of measurement points, thus providing a higher level of details of the wing model under load. The research summarized above shows that FBG sensors can meet the requirements on distributed pressure sensors. However, the FBGs used have a diameter ≥ 2 mm which is too large to effectively be built into composite wing structures. Commercially are also Fabry-Perot sensors available, which measure the pressure in the end of the fibre. However, this type of sensor only allows point measurements. The FBGs presented in earlier studies are added to the surface of the component, thereby vulnerable to surface loads. Older types of sensors integrated into composites have in some cases reduced the mechanical performance of the material since having large radie, around 3 mm or larger.

Wing surface pressure monitoring on an aircraft with traditional technology will employ hundreds of electrically connected sensors on the wing. This is a bulky, complex and costly solution and, therefore, only used in on ground wind tunnel tests today. For measurements during service, there is no existing pressure monitoring system today. In this scenario, optical fibre solutions based on Fibre-Bragg Gratings (FBGs) [3,7,8] are advantageous due to their capability to be seamlessly embedded into lightweight aircraft composite parts, multipoint sensing possibility and immunity to electromagnetic interferences.

In this study optical fibres with FBGs have been used for creating quasi-distributed pressure sensors that can be embedded into surface materials for composite structures.

To enhance the pressure sensitivity, FEM (Finite Element Method) was used to identify the best combination of materials for the coating, upcoating and buffer.

The main goal has been to develop compact and robust sensors/sensor materials that measure pressures from 10 to 200 kPa.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The FEM study showed that the highest sensitivity could be achieved with a thicker layer of a soft material between the fiber optics diameter (125 μ m) and the external buffer diameter (limited to 1mm in this study). Several materials were studied for the fiber coating, upcoating and buffering. The combination of the different materials and dimensions were evaluated and the most promising combinations were fabricated for tests.

The sensor used for this experiment was FBGs inscribed in 125 μ m optical fiber having either Polyimide (PI) or Acrylate (Ac) as original coating. The wavelength shift of an FBG can be related to strain, and its sensitivity is approximately 1.2 pm/ μ strain. To make the FBG sensitive for pressure the optical fibers were coated with a soft up-coating layer of Silicone and a stiffer buffer material (see figure 1). The total outer diameter was 1 mm. Four different types of fibres were manufactured with combinations of the two original coating materials and two different buffer materials that were either Polyamide (PA) or Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) (see table 1). The Central Wave length (CW) for each FBG is presented in table 1.

Figure 1: Principle of the pressure-sensitive fibre-optic sensor: the combination of upcoating the fibre and a buffer material changes external pressure to an axial strain, enhancing the sensitivity to pressure.

Identification	Original Coating	Up-Coating	Buffer	Surface material	Central wave length (CW) [nm]
AC-SI-PEEK-1	Acrylate	Silicone	PEEK	Amspand	1534.79
AC-SI-Nylon-1	Acrylate	Silicone	Polyamide	Amspand	1554.4
PI-SI-PEEK-1	Polyimide	Silicone	PEEK	Amspand	1544.4
PI-SI-Nylon-1	Polyimide	Silicone	Polyamide	Amspand	1539.596
AC-SI-PEEK-2	Acrylate	Silicone	PEEK	Epoxy	1539.5
AC-SI-Nylon-2	Acrylate	Silicone	Polyamide	Epoxy	1549.315
PI-SI-PEEK-2	Polyimide	Silicone	PEEK	Only tested alone	1549.058
PI-SI-Nylon-2	Polyimide	Silicone	Polyamide	Epoxy	1534.38

Table 1: Test samples configuration coating, buffer and composite surface material.

The pressure sensitivity of the coated optical fibres was first measured for the fibres alone in a pressure chamber. In the next test step, the coated optical fibres were built into a couple of different types of surface materials on top of pre-cured 4 mm carbon fibre /epoxy (CFRP) laminates. The CFRP was built up of 7 layers of Hexcel prepreg M49/HS/600 gsm. The surface material was either a syntactic foam material (Amspand) with a 0.1 mm glass fibre/epoxy cover layer (Delta DT120/823) or 10 epoxy film layers (36 gsm Hexcel 6376 resin) with a 0.1 mm glass fibre/epoxy cover layer (see figure 2).

Figure 2: Fibre optics build into a) Amspan surface material b) Epoxy surface material.

The pressure response of the inbuilt optical fibres was tested in an Instron Machine (see figure 3) in load steps of 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 200 kPa. Each load step contained a one minute hold. The pressure was calculated from the machine compression force and the pressure area.

Figure 3: Test set-up in the Instron Machine.

3 RESULTS

The test in the pressure chamber of the single FBG fibres showed hysteresis during the measurements. However, the best results were obtained with the PI coated fiber with PEEK buffer. When the fibres were built into surface material on the top of CFRP laminates, and tested in the Instron Machine, the effect of the hysteresis was less pronounced. The best combination for pressure sensitivity was either to use an optical fibre with PI coating and PEEK buffer or an optical fibre with Ac coating and PA buffer, combined with the syntactic foam (Amspan) surface cover material (see figure 4).

Figure 4: Results from pressure test. 1 was built into Amspan surface material and 2 was built into epoxy surface material.

3 DISCUSSIONS

the test results with the unembedded up-coated and buffered optical fibres did show hysteresis, while the laminates with embedded up-coated and buffered optical fibres, in the syntactic foam (Amspan) did not. This is not in line with a previous study that showed hysteresis when using the Amspan as a buffer material instead of PEEK or Polyamide (PA) in stand-alone measurements with the fibres. However, in the laminate configuration with optical fibres embedded into the surface material on CFRP laminate a 0.1 mm glass fibre/epoxy cover layer was also used on top of the surface material. This glass layer might have a faster recovery due to its stiffness and that might have helped the hysteresis effect to be less pronounced. The measurements of the laminates with the epoxy surface material did show less pressure response compared to the laminates with the Amspan surface material. This is not a surprise

since the epoxy material is much stiffer than the Amspand material.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this study was to use optical fibres with FBGs for quasi-distributed pressure sensors that could be embedded into surface materials for composite structures. The main goal was to develop compact and robust sensors/sensor materials that measure pressures from 10 to 200 kPa. The study showed that the best combination for pressure sensitivity was either to use an optical fibre with Polyimide coating and Polyetheretherketone buffer or an optical fibre with Acrylate coating and Polyamide buffer, combined with the syntactic foam (Amspand) surface cover material topped with a 0.1 mm glass fibre/epoxy cover layer. The study also showed that the embedded sensors was sensitive for pressure in the required pressure range.

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